

KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: use cases description extended report

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Abstract (in German)

Dieser Bericht erweitert die Beschreibungen der Anwendungsfälle und gibt Empfehlungen für die Zuweisung von Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) unterhalb der Studienebene, d. h. hier, als erster Ansatz, einer Variablen innerhalb eines Datensatzes. Die Empfehlungen beziehen sich auf die Datentypen und Dienste der Anwendungsfallpartner. Sie würden jedoch auch anderen Einrichtungen zugute kommen, z. B. Datenarchiven, die über Tabellendaten verfügen und die Vorteile einer eindeutigen Identifizierung ihrer Daten auf einer niedrigeren Granularitätsebene nutzen möchten. Der Bericht beschreibt sieben Anwendungsfälle von vier Konsortialpartnern aus dem KonsortSWD. Die Zielelemente, die eine PID erhalten sollen, sind Variablen in großen und kleinen Datensätzen, PIDs für Informationsbündel (Gruppe von Variablen) und qualitative Daten, wie Beobachtungsaufzeichnungen, Interviews und Transkriptionen. PIDs für Variablen, die von Harmonisierungsinstrumenten verwendet werden, sind ebenfalls enthalten. Die Institutionen sind dafür verantwortlich, die Variable oder ein anderes Attribut, für das sie eine PID erhalten möchten, zu dokumentieren und die URL der Landing Page sowie die Metadatenätze an [dalra](#) zu übermitteln, um eine PID zu erhalten. Zu diesem Zweck wurde der [dalra](#) PID-Registrierungsdienst im Rahmen der KonsortSWD-Maßnahme TA.5-M.1 erweitert. Das [dalra](#) registriert dann die entsprechenden Metadaten und holt sich die PID im Namen der Einrichtung und gibt die PID an die Einrichtung zurück, die die Daten mit den entsprechenden PIDs speichert.

Abstract

This report extends the use case descriptions and provides recommendations for assigning Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) below the study level, i.e., here, as a first approach, a variable within a dataset. The recommendations rely on use case partners' data types and services. However, it would also benefit other institutions, such as data repositories that hold tabular data and want to take advantage of uniquely identifying their data at a lower granularity level. The report describes seven use cases from four consortium partners from KonsortSWD. The target elements to get a PID are variables within large and small datasets, PIDs for information bundles (group of variables), and qualitative data, such as observation recording, interviews and transcriptions. PIDs for variables used by harmonization tools are also included. Institutions will

be responsible for documenting the variable or other attribute they want to get a PID for, providing the landing page URL and metadata records to dalra to get a PID. To this end, the dalra PID registration service was enlarged under the KonsortSWD Measure TA.5-M.1. The dalra will then register the corresponding metadata and get the PID on behalf of the institution, returning the PID to the institution, which will store the data with the corresponding PIDs.

Keywords:

Persistent Identifiers - PIDs. Research data citation. Research data - Social Sciences. Variables - Social Sciences. Granularity level identification. Research data services - technical infrastructure. Use cases descriptions.

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KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: use cases description extended report

1. Background and Scope

The NFDI¹-funded consortium KonsortSWD, Task Area 5, Measure 1: TA.5-M.1 "*Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure*", provides a technical solution designed to fulfil the increasing demand-driven data services of the research data infrastructure. It aims to make data findability and accessibility on the level of inline data objects of studies more efficient. Particularly in the Social Sciences, PIDs are commonly available on the study or dataset levels, which is insufficient to unambiguously identify the information used and ensure an accurate data citation. The KonsortSWD TA.5-M.1 seeks to enhance the state of the art of citing research data by developing an infrastructure to reference detailed attributes, initially variables within such data. By assigning PIDs to lower attributes, individual elements of the datasets can be referenced and retrieved with the required metadata for machine-actionable and human access. Referencing research data and their inherited detailed entities by Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) supports FAIR² data usage. Using one data point - the PID - boosts data citation, direct data access, and data reuse.

The first report³ about this service provided two major use cases namely *data citation* for publications and *data access* for variables, which were enabled with the general function for registering variables with a persistent identifier. The first report scope also included the useful background to understanding the current data citation landscape:

- the Social Sciences research data-related challenges;
- the hurdles of data citation below study level, and
- the data granularity level relevancy for the domain.

Furthermore, the previous report delivered the PID assignment service requirements. The necessary metadata schema and the envisioned system architecture were explained. The system is conceived to provide a general, maintainable, and scalable infrastructure that enables the registration of PIDs to the level of attributes, i.e., a variable in Social Science research data.

In line with KonsortSWD partners, use cases for assigning PIDs to data elements below the study level have been developed. This report provides descriptions of all the use cases of assigning a PID to elements below study and dataset levels where a proof-of-concept has been achieved with partners. In this sense, this report extends the previous use case descriptions, providing recommendations for assigning Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) below the study level, i.e., here, as a first approach, a variable within a dataset. The best practice recommendations rely on use case partners' data types and services. The report also highlights the RDCs' advantages of uniquely identifying their data below datasets at a lower granularity level. However, it would also benefit other institutions, such as data repositories holding tabular data. The projects and use case partners enclosed in this report are:

¹ Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (<https://www.nfdi.de>) as part of NFDI under project number 442494171.

² FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. It refers to the FAIR Data Principles developed by the FORCE 11 community, that recommend data should be shared according to these four concepts.

³ Klas, Claus-Peter, Zloch, Matthäus, Bach, Janete Saldanha, Baran, Erdal, & Mutschke, Peter. (2022). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>

- HEADS project⁴ from the German Center for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW);
- GESIS Data Archive⁵ (SDC Survey Data Curation) from the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (GESIS);
- GESIS harmonization tools: QuestionLink⁶, HaSpaad⁷ and Onbound⁸;
- SOEP-Core⁹ from the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW);
- Qualiservice¹⁰ from the University of Bremen.

Following this section 1, we describe the service scope and applicability and how the service is conceived. In the concept proofing section, we demonstrate the registration process in a comprehensive view, demonstrating how stakeholders interact within the process and what are their broader activities. In section 2, we provide a detailed problem description of why finding and accessing the data at a variable level without a PID is time-consuming and hinders data reuse. Our problem-solving approach is then detailed, demonstrating how lower-level PIDs can boost data citation and retrieval. Section 3 describes the use case partners' context, their projects, and how PIDs for variables will address their users' needs. Each section on the use descriptions has been reviewed by the respective use case partner. Section 4 concludes the reports as a relevant approach in an increasingly intensive data-driven research ecosystem, and section 5 informs the envisioned activities and deliverables within the KonsortSWD.

1.1. Scope and applicability

The service assigns a PID that references (points to) digital objects, fine-grained referencing and identification items within data research and particular documents (inline objects). Our lower granular level approach aligns with the Group of European Data Experts (GEDE) - in Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) Forum. These institutions consider that the granularity level is related to the smallest part of a digital object that it is reasonable to refer to and cite and is thus connected to both collections as well as subsetting, and best practices are by necessity quite domain specific.

One of the most common data formats in the Social Sciences are surveys and questionnaires results, a tabular dataset frequently stored in statistical packages files such as R or Stata and spreadsheets or comma-separated values (.csv) files. This database structure is shaped as variables, distributed as rows (which contain objects) and columns (which contain properties) within datasets. Data files from these datasets are created using the information gathered via surveys, which is based on the unit of observation (e.g., an individual, a residence, a corporation, or another element). Variables are used to hold the data for each unit. Variables are frequently maintained as coded values (numeric format), and they may comprise data informed by the respondent or other means (e.g., observations, calculations, recordings). Our domain specifications rely on the Social Sciences field inferences. The object can be a variable from tabular data, a set of variables or a subset of data. However, to fulfil our use cases needs, and as

⁴ https://www.dzhw.eu/gmbh/index_html

⁵ <https://search.gesis.org/home>

⁶ <https://www.gesis.org/angebot/daten-aufbereiten-und-analysieren/question-link>

⁷ Harmonizing and synthesizing partnership histories

<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/harmonizing-and-synthesizing-partnership-histories>

⁸ ONBound - Old and new boundaries: National Identities and Religion

<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/onbound>

⁹ German Socio-Economic Panel Study (SOEP-Core) <https://paneldata.org/soep-core/>

¹⁰ <https://www.qualiservice.org>

a second approach, we also address the dalra registration service to assign PIDs to individual files containing qualitative data (e.g., interviews' transcripts) of a dataset, a specific segment in the audio or video file (e.g., as parts of interviews and voice recordings), and to specific elements within the paper (e.g., figures, charts, and tables).

The general steps toward PID registration are validating the minimum metadata schema, registering the PID, and storing the metadata. The expected results benefit data producers and reusers, making research data easier to find and cite. It also increases research data availability and findability, intensifying reuse and reproducibility approaches. Since individual elements of the data files can be machine-readable, a range of features using scripts (do-files from Stata, R scripts) can be applied to allow data automated access. For instance, an R code would run over the variable's PID and lead the researcher to obtain the exact variable data from that dataset; Consequently, this is a faster way to reach data reused, with fewer steps if a PID is unavailable.

2. Proof of concept

This section describes the service conceptualisation based on the problem description and the solution approached by the PID assignment service to the variable level. How relevant stakeholders interplay with the service instance and what features they can take advantage of are depicted in Figure 1 – PID assignment landscape: a comprehensive process view.

Figure 1 is a business process model (BPM¹¹) based example of a high-level service deliverable and the interaction within the process. The stakeholders in this landscape are the research institute or individual researchers, which provide collected data, the research data centre (RDC), the data stewardship, the dalra infrastructure (the entity providing the PID registration service) and the research community. The PID assignment is the service instance, a vital part of the process. While conceptually distinct in figure 1, the research institutions and the research community may be considered integrated as a single stakeholder since these institutions belong to the scientific community. However, considering their role in this process, research institutions, as the data-provider in this model, allow a broader community to find and reuse (playing the data re-users role) research outputs they produce and make available through Research Data Centres (RDCs). In the sense of their agency, research institutions/researchers and the community are treated as distinct stakeholders here.

When a research institute (or a researcher) shares their outputs, they also provide the research data, which constitutes the evidence of its findings. Many Research Data Centres responsible for archiving those datasets need to carry on some data curation activities to comply with communities' best practices on indexing, citation, information retrieval, and long-term preservation. Considering that our target granularity level model relies on Social Science research data, initially tabular data, the variable is the most interesting fine-grained data level here, and it has to be documented to get a PID. Once metadata records are submitted and PIDs are requested to the dalra user interface, the application validates each metadata field. The PID proposal is then delivered to the RDC. If the metadata validator finds any inconsistency, an error message warns the service requester, and the user can update or adjust any incorrect information and submit the PID request again. If the requester does not provide corrected metadata records, the PID will not be assigned, and the process will end.

¹¹ Association of Business Process Management Professionals International. *Guide to the Business Process Management Body of Knowledge (BPM CBOK®)*. Version 4.0 November 11, 2019.

Once the PID is issued, its records are stored in the variable PID assignment service, an instance of the dalra service, and the RDC gets the variable PID(s). When the PID(s) is (are) assigned to the variable(s), then the visibility and findability of research data are increased. If an automatic way is provided, for instance, through an R script, researchers can quickly access the data per se. Since data findability and availability favour reusability, other researchers can also quickly reuse and provide data citations. They can identify the most specific data grained-level they reused, reporting the variable PID. The research community can also develop new studies and answer exciting research questions based on secondary data analysis, providing new research data when combining new uses of secondary data and collecting further information.

Figure 1 – PID assignment landscape: a comprehensive process view
* PID assignment workflow¹²

¹² PID assignment workflow is represented in figure 7 available at Klas, Claus-Peter, Matthäus Zloch, Janete Saldanha Bach, Erdal Baran, and Peter Mutschke. 2022. KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>.

Without a PID at lower granularity levels within the dataset, data practitioners cannot provide a unique identification to cite the exact data unambiguously when referencing at the variable level. A detailed citation is essential because researchers commonly reuse partial results from available survey data that interest them most, not necessarily the entire dataset. For instance, specific data regarding targeted information from a dataset benefits their research question, taking into account the various factors of relevance, usability and quality (Koesten *et al.*, 2020)¹³. When searching for structured data, Koesten *et al.* (2020) also point out that among other relevant aspects, users also consider basic statistics about the dataset, such as counts and value ranges, and information about the data granularity as one significant attribute that matters when selecting data for reuse purposes. To this end, documentation is essential to understand variables and samples. On the other hand, finding the reused variable in papers for scrutiny and reproducibility is a complex, time-consuming, and discouraging process when a detailed citation is unavailable, even though Kern and Mathiak (2015)¹⁴ suggest that social scientists understand that spend more time in data searching is inherent to the research process. The processes for finding and accessing data using or not a PID and its related advantages and disadvantages are described in the next section.

2.1. The problem description: finding and accessing the data at a variable level without a PID

Due to funders' compliance and publishing or institutional requirements, research data have been more and more publicly available. Researchers and data repositories also aim to increase their data findability¹⁵ and visibility¹⁶, favouring data findability and leading to reuse and reproducibility practices. Once researchers can find and obtain a dataset, they are interested in, a long and exhausting process takes place to enable them to identify the most relevant information and get the data from these datasets, which do not provide a PID at a variable level. In this sense, researchers must:

1. find data citation in the paper text: In case researchers are not aware of a specific survey or study they want to get data, they need to seek and find the data citation in the text of a study of interest: looking at relevant papers for the study's citations, questions quoted, or any other "hint" as a website or the dataset provider institution name;
2. discover the study or source of data: once they find a dataset of interest, they need to discover and access the dataset at the data provider's website;
3. check the dataset version: Then, it is necessary to check the appropriate version, if applicable. Some studies can also cite data from previous dataset versions available on the data provider website;
4. find and read data documentation: users need to look into the data documentation, read it and make inferences;

¹³ Koesten, L., Simperl, E., Kacprzak, E., Blount, T., Tennison, J. (2020). Everything you always wanted to know about a dataset: Studies in data summarisation. *Int. J. Hum.-Comput. Stud.* 135, C (Mar 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2019.10.004>

¹⁴ Kern, D., Mathiak, B. (2015). Are there any differences in data set retrieval compared to well-known literature retrieval? In: Kapidakis, S., Mazurek, C., Werla, M. (eds.) *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries*, pp. 197–208. Springer, Berlin.

¹⁵ Fidan Limani, Yousef Younes, Valentina Hiseni, Janete Saldanha Bach, Peter Mutschke, & Brigitte Mathiak. (2021). *KonsortSWD Task Area 5 Measure 2 Report Scope: Milestones 1, 2, and 3 (0.95)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5901207>

¹⁶ Limani, Fidan, Bach, Janete Saldanha, Hiseni, Valentina, & Mathiak, Brigitte. (2022). *Enhancing data findability: how scientists and repositories can improve their data visibility (2.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6900267>

5. seek for the variables in the documentation: they need to check for the variables that best match the referenced data in the paper they have read;
6. getting access to the dataset: Before getting access to data, it is necessary to be informed what the access rules (if data is open, with limited access or have any specific rule to access restricted/sensitive data, such as a contract) are; In case of restrictions rules, they need to apply for data access, if applicable, depending on the resource's access governing conditions;
7. check how to open the files from the dataset: once the dataset is located and accessed, it is necessary to open the file, depending on the format using specific software or driver;
8. download the dataset: Fulfilled all conditions, the user can download and obtain a given dataset that will be possible to open and reuse;
9. open the dataset and find the variables and its values: to this end users can locate the variables data manually, depending on the file type (CSV, spreadsheets) or get the data using statistical software commands;
10. applying statistics: users need to understand the variable's values, combining and/or analyse information;
11. reuse the variables: users will provide new inferences and alternative analyses on the same dataset, reusing the data they need;
12. provide the data citation: without a PID, users will probably cite it again as a dataset name, a dataset provider name or a report or study the variable was published, restarting the non-standard citation cycle.

The process of accessing and reusing variables without a PID is depicted in figure 2 – workflow 1: reusing variables without PIDs.

Accessing and reusing variables without PID

Figure 2 – workflow 1: reusing variables without PIDs

The workflow depicted in Figure 2 is a time-consuming and error-prone process to reuse data. In this sense, a solution that mitigates the ambiguity risks is designed and described below, provided by the PID registration service.

2.2. Service approach to solving the problem

Beyond providing the digital object's identity for publicising information source and retrieval, citations attribute credit and intellectual property to guarantee the ownership of intellectual products. Research outputs (such as papers and dissertations) are classic examples of highly structured scientific and scholarly communication citations. Even though publications and data differ in authorship functions¹⁷, the datasets' identities' attributions regard research results' credibility and reputation. In data reuse practice, one of the FAIR principles' cornerstones, data citation is the strongest tie between data sources and results from the reused data. Data citation promotes the ethical use of data and fosters credibility results. However, as a common practice, assigning a PID to a whole dataset is not enough to identify variables; consequently, not suitable to properly ensure the specific data citation. Since researchers can provide inferences and recommendations from secondary data analyses as research question outcomes, it is highly relevant to ensure trustworthy and credible results through the specific data identification and

¹⁷ Birnholtz, Jeremy P. (2006). What does it mean to be an author? The intersection of credit, contribution, and collaboration in science. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57, 13 (November 2006), 1758–1770.

what variables were reused. Using a PID will guarantee precision, uniqueness, and traceable data citation. Even though authors try to add data sources, descriptions and details in the text, it is not a disambiguate-proof method due to the lack of citation standards adoption.

Figure 3 is a high-level image of the data granularity levels within the Social Sciences and depicts our service approach to assigning a PID at a lower level. The PIDs are commonly assigned to the study and dataset's levels, a set of datasets (collections). Our proposal considers extending the current practice and assigning a PID at a variable level. We also consider assigning a PID on the question level as a future extension.

The PID registration is an extension of the existent service at *dalra*¹⁸, which already assigns PIDs to complete datasets or a collection of datasets (using the DOI¹⁹ system). In the sense of providing a PID to the variable level to enable precise citation and solving the variable ambiguously identification problem, the *dalra* PID assignment service is being extended with a register variable's service. To this end, the *dalra* service will assign a PID with Handle standard, using a PID as a third-party registration process service (ePIC API). Institutions will be responsible for documenting the variable they want to get a PID for, providing a variable landing page URL along with the metadata records to *dalra* registration service. The variables' documenting is a PID registration service requirement.

The service also enables "bulk registration," which means the registration of many variables at once. It requires the user to register a variable that provides a landing page and the minimal metadata schema such as Study or Dataset DOI, variable name, variable label, landing page, resource type, title, creators, publisher, publication date, availability, and relations with other entities.

Figure 3 – granularity level for PIDs

¹⁸ *dalra* is the PID registration agency service in Germany for social science and economic data, supported by GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences and ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics.

¹⁹ The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) system registration to the dataset level is offered through *dalra* in cooperation with DataCite, the international initiative to establish easier access to digital research data.

Data holders institutions will be responsible for documenting the variable they want to get a PID for, providing a variable landing page URL along with the metadata records to dalra registration service. The variables' documenting is a service requirement. To register the variables, the dalra service will then register the metadata and get the Handle IDs on behalf of the institutions, which will store the data with the corresponding PIDs. The variables registration metadata schema is available in the KonsortSWD_TA51_Metadata Schema extension report²⁰, also as examples in the use case description section.

The following section describes the process of the data citation using PID at a variable level to find and get access to the data.

2.3. Data citation and retrieval using PIDs

Assigning PIDs to the variables improves data findability and accessibility because PIDs are machine-readable and allow machine-actionable features. The relationships with other entities can be indexed using controlled vocabulary terms, allowing metasearch and meta-browsing. Many digital objects can be brought together, and all related items can deliver a more comprehensive overview of associations, forming, for example, a knowledge graph (see Section 5 on potential future work).

If one PID is registered for each variable, automated scripts (do-files, R scripts, etc.) can be applied to quickly obtain the selected data from the dataset, taking advantage of information about the variables also registered in the statistical files (i.e., STATA or SPSS). Some conditions are required to automated access, such as: only one dataset is registered per DOI, that's used to register the PID for a variable, the dataset is not restricted or closed access, and a REST API is available. The explicitly variable name, label and response scales are documented within research data statistical files. Once the technical requisites are met, these automated scripts can technically give access to the data for direct usage without downloading the SPSS/STATA file, either the complete dataset or singled-out variables via PIDs²¹.

Figure 4 depicts the workflow for accessing and reusing variables with PIDs. Researchers can take advantage of these machine-actionable features when data is identified with a PID, which can link to the original dataset and the precise variable. Getting data through automated access is a faster way to reach and reuse data, going through fewer steps if a PID is unavailable, compared to Figure 4.

²⁰ Bach, Janete Saldanha, Klas, Claus-Peter & Mutschke, Peter. (2023, January 31). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: metadata schema extended report. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588902>.

²¹ Klas, Claus-Peter, & Hopt, Oliver. (2022, December 7). DDI Variable Documentation and data access using R. EDDI - European User Conference on DDI, Paris, France. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7408629>.

Accessing and reusing variables with a PID

Figure 4 - workflow 2: reusing variables with PIDs

Besides advantages from end-user perspectives of getting, reusing, and citing data, the Research Data Centres (RDCs) also directly benefit from data governance activities and their provided services. The registration service requires a metadata schema to identify the variable's core elements and its relationships with other variables and entities of the same or different studies. Explicit these relations favour the formation of a network out of these connections into a knowledge graph representation²² (see Section 5 on potential future work).

²² Bach, Janete Saldanha, Klas, Claus-Peter, & Zapilko, Benjamin. (2022, November 30). A controlled vocabulary for a social science knowledge graph. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7389936>

3. Use cases description

This section describes the service solutions based on the partners' use case needs. Each institution selected as a use case participates in the KonsortSWD and plays an essential role in shaping the service, testing the concept, and providing helpful feedback on the RDC daily activities associated with the Persistent Identifiers. The following use case descriptions are: the Higher Education Analytical Data System (HEADS)²³ project from the German Center for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW); the GESIS Data Archive²⁴ from the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (GESIS), including the GESIS harmonization tools: QuestionLink²⁵, HaSpaad²⁶ and Onbound²⁷; the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP-Core)²⁸, a longitudinal study from the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW); and the Qualiservice²⁹ qualitative data collection from the University of Bremen.

3.1. The German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)

The German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW³⁰) conducts application-oriented empirical research on higher education and science systems. With its data and analyses, the DZHW supports politics, universities, and educational administration in developing higher education in Germany and Europe. The use case concerns the "Higher Education Analytical Data System (HEADS)" project at the DZHW. The project is establishing a sustainable, flexible, and expandable digital reporting system that visualises data for monitoring purposes.

HEADS represents the digital transformation of the DZHW's reporting. Following the digital transformation and the new technical possibilities associated with it, the presentation of key indicators and parameters of education monitoring has changed extensively, as examples from Great Britain or the Netherlands illustrate (UK: HESA – Higher Education Statistics Agency UK³¹; Netherlands: Nuffic – The Dutch Organisation for Internationalisation in Education³²). With the project HEADS, the DZHW is initiating a comprehensive process of digital change management in the reporting of its panel studies and cross-sectional surveys (e.g., Student Life Cycle Panel, The Student Survey in Germany), thus connecting to current technical developments and forms of presentation.

The aim of the digital transformation of the DZHW's reporting is to present the main indicators of education monitoring to the various stakeholders as well as to an interested professional public in a flexible and contemporary web-based manner. Therefore, a new digitalised format of reporting survey results, especially those of the long-term survey series, is to be introduced

²³ https://www.dzhw.eu/gmbh/index_html

²⁴ <https://www.gesis.org/home>

²⁵ <https://www.gesis.org/angebot/daten-aufbereiten-und-analysieren/question-link>

²⁶ Harmonizing and synthesizing partnership histories

<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/harmonizing-and-synthesizing-partnership-histories>

²⁷ ONBound - Old and new boundaries: National Identities and Religion

<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/onbound>

²⁸ German Socio-Economic Panel Study (SOEP-Core) <https://paneldata.org/soep-core/>

²⁹ <https://www.qualiservice.org>

³⁰ Cf. https://www.dzhw.eu/gmbh/index_html.

³¹ Cf. <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/>

³² Cf. <https://www.nuffic.nl/en/subjects/facts-and-figures>

in the framework of the envisaged *digital reporting (digital reports)*. For this purpose, selected results will be made available in graphic form in an *information portal*, in close coordination with the funding agencies and with due regard for data protection. The digital reporting format has the advantage of being easily accessible and flexible concerning presentation requirements. The export of results shall be possible in various formats (graphic files in .png, tables in .xls, PDF or Presentation).

In addition to the flexible reporting of key indicators for international and national education monitoring at the national level, digital transformation also supplies the technical means to provide both federal states and higher education institutions with nationwide (reference) values for steering purposes. With this essential innovation, the DZHW strengthens the service orientation of its statutory tasks in a sustainable manner. The envisaged information portal and the digital reporting on the DZHW survey series play a crucial role, especially in enlisting universities to participate in the surveys. In return for their support in accessing the field, universities can obtain not only nationwide reference values, but also university-specific values (password-protected). The digital transformation of reporting also has the advantage of expandability: a joint information platform for presenting the results of all DZHW surveys is to be created in the long run.

To sum up, HEADS – Higher Education Analytical Data System pursues the following objectives:

- **use of (inter)nationally common forms of visualisation and presentation** to display survey results and education indicators in graphs and tables, in compliance with data protection regulations (export options PDF, Excel, graphic/image file .png, PowerPoint);
- **establishment of a sustainable, flexible, and expandable digital reporting system** that will make the survey results of the DZHW accessible in a contemporary web-based manner and, prospectively, serve as a joint portal for the presentation of the results of all DZHW surveys;
- **extension of the range of services for federal states and higher education institutions** by making state and federal (reference) values and university-specific values available to higher education institutions in a password-protected form in return for their support in accessing the field;
- **strengthening the research orientation**, as using standardised and automated procedures in digital reporting creates scope for research and, particularly for scientific publication activities.

A standard of data citation is needed to make the results of HEADS widely usable and citable. The PID system is particularly suitable for this purpose, as it assigns PIDs to (1) individual variables and (2) entire information packages that comprise a central reporting variable (“indicator”) and the related multivariate analyses conducted in HEADS. Both professionals and interested public will benefit from employing and citing data with the help of PIDs. With this use case, there are two possibilities of assigning a PID:

1. PIDs for each variable, i.e., for each indicator or differentiation variable;
2. PIDs for information packages

Following, each digital object target for PIDs is described.

3.1.1. PIDs for each variable

Table 1 shows each variable that is assigned a PID to identify the variable directly:

Variables_label	ziwahr01	ziwahr02	ziwahr03	ziwahr04	ziwahr05
Indicator_name	obtain admission to vocational training or study programme for the desired profession	create or design beautiful things	have very good chances of advancing professionally	have very interesting work content	have a good match of job requirements and own abilities
very likely	23.619	10.431	9.434	18.997	12.35
likely	46.243	23.122	44.459	45.448	49.606
partly-partly	25.465	35.068	39.408	29.94	33.361
unlikely	3.703	17.844	5.806	4.908	4.042
very unlikely	0.971	13.534	0.892	0.707	0.641

Table 1: Example 1 - PIDs for each variable

In the following example, the PID is assigned on each variable, as depicted in figure 5:

Figure 5: PID assignment representation for each variable

Another example is a variable PID which is assigned to differentiation variables, as shown in figure 6:

Figure 6 – PID assignment on differentiation variables

3.1.2. PIDs for entire information packages consisting of a central reporting variable/theoretical construct (“indicator”) and the related multivariate analyses

HEADS uses (inter)nationally common forms of visualisation and presentation in the graphs and tables that document the survey results and education indicators. It offers many export options, with formats such as PDFs, spreadsheets, graphs/images in .png files or presentations. Thus, the PIDs should identify as one single output a set containing elements such as the indicator construct and its univariate distribution as well as contingency tables (derived from several differentiation variables) that can be presented as tables or graphs. For illustration, see Figure 7 – PID assignment to the intersection analysis from the digital reporting system:

Figure 7: PID assigned to the intersection analyses from the digital reporting system

As dependent variables may consist of several items, multiple intersections are possible. Table 2 shows the dependent and the independent variables. In this case, the dependent variable consists of several items that belong to a larger theoretical construct. Several independent variables allow for differentiating the dependent variable according to subgroups: gender, educational background, migration background, and school types. In this example, the dependent variable refers to the target group's goals and achievements. These goals are operationalised as five so-called *ziwahr* variables. These variables are analysed concerning the independent variables gender, educational background, migration background, and school types. An information package is provided which shows the values of the dependent variables (*ziwahr01-05*) according to the differentiation variables (gender, educational background, migration background, school types). For users, the interesting thing is that there is a place where the information, differentiated for subgroups or various differentiation variables, is permanently stored so it can be located and cited. It is irrelevant whether users want to use only the value of a subgroup, a comparison of subgroups, or a comparison of the differences according to different differentiation variables. Hence there should be a PID for the information package that enables all these different purposes.

Indicator Dependent variable		Differentiation variables							
		Gender		Educational background		Migration background		School type	
Indicator_label	Indicator_name	Male	Female	Non-academic	Academic	Without migration background	With migration background	General school	Vocational school
ziwahr01	obtain admission to vocational ...	72.603	67.53	68.472	71.467	71.611	64.274	71.218	67.29
ziwahr02	create or design ...	30.124	36.607	32.825	34.097	32.752	36.115	32.888	34.801
ziwahr03	have very good chances...	59.896	48.628	52.523	55.31	54.677	51.381	53.494	54.651
ziwahr04	have very interesting ...	64.169	64.788	63.206	65.899	66.367	58.28	65.947	61.601
ziwahr05	have a good match...	62.529	61.529	60.674	63.241	63.131	58.186	62.8	60.365

Table 2 – Example 2 – PID for information package (one indicator and several related analyses)

Figure 8 is a schematic representation which illustrates that each variable involved has a PID, but also the entire information package for which the analysis procedures applied are stored in the background.

Figure 8: PID assignment to each variable and the information package as a whole

Since the PID is always connected to a “Landing Page”, the data holder can define the level of data for which to get the PID and describe them on the landing page. The management of HEADS has approved the use of persistent identifiers for the DZHW data in order to facilitate citations by researchers, taking into account the relations of dependent and independent variables, as well as multivariate analysis. The PIDs at lower levels will reliably identify these entities and allow for more transparent citations.

3.2. GESIS Use cases

GESIS – the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences provides essential and internationally relevant research-based services for the social sciences. Among those services are survey studies on crucial social issues that have been investigating human behaviour through decades, consequently generating vast amounts of data in the variable format from questionnaires. For GESIS, registering variables is a strategic approach towards enhancing FAIR data research management, both from the data holder’s standpoint as well as from the researcher’s perspective. Considering the variables PID to expand GESIS end-users advantages, it stands as an added-value service for improving transparency, reducing time and effort for data citation, and increasing the incentives for data reuse. The first milestone from TA5 M1 report³³ provided GESIS use cases on data citation made easier and accessing data to the variable level in a disambiguating manner, reducing the human mistakes in tracking data through study

³³ Klas, Claus-Peter, Matthäus Zloch, Janete Saldanha Bach, Erdal Baran, and Peter Mutschke. 2022. KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>.

documentation. More use cases regarding GESIS services are described in subsections, including Gesis search and variables harmonisation tools such as QuestionLink, GESIS ONBound, and GESIS HaSpaD projects.

3.2.1. GESIS Data Archive

The Gesis Data Archive³⁴ is a data platform that contains information about social science research data and open-access publications. Following a user-centred design approach, the study descriptions are linked with the associated datasets, which are also available for download. GESIS data archive offers more than 6,500 national and international studies for secondary analysis that can be ordered in a user-friendly way. Users can find research data as variables from questionnaires from relevant social science surveys data, such as the General Population Survey of the Social Sciences (ALLBUS), General Population Survey of the Social Sciences (ISSP), Eurobarometer, Politbarometer, German Longitudinal Election Study (GLES), European Values Study (EVS), GESIS Panel (GPANEL), Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), among others. More than 500,000 variables from those studies cover a wide range of topics in the Social Sciences, Economics, and Behaviour Sciences, such as the social structure of the population in the Federal Republic of Germany as well as at the European level, political attitudes of voters and candidates, opinions on family, work, religion, politics and society and competencies of adults.

GESIS search use case on PID for variables addresses precise citation on secondary data analysis and data discoverability and accessibility through automatic access. Given the large datasets cumulated across studies and waves, dataset versions changes. PIDs are the more accurate form to differentiate repeated variables through the years, simultaneously ensuring straight access through automatic features. If catalogued, questions can also be assigned with a PID. The following is a hypothetical example since questions still need to be documented. However, this example brings another valuable perspective on solutions based on PIDs' machine-actionable functionalities.

- **Use case 1: Reuse of questions/instruments**

a) Frank has raised funds from the DFG to conduct an online survey. He wants to explain attitudes toward reforming pension insurance with an approach based on the theory of rational choice. For his survey, it is not necessary to redevelop the entire questionnaire. On the contrary, he would like to adopt established measuring instruments on political ideology and voting behaviour from the GLES, questions on the employment biography from the ALLBUS, and questions on income and wealth from the SOEP. Frank uses a program for the questionnaire creation that DDI can read as XML, which he has programmed in R. Using the question search, he identifies the URIs for the desired questions and imports the DDI metadata into his questionnaire tool. His tool allows the questionnaire to be output as an XML, HTML, or PDF file. The documents always contain the URI to the original question with the recommended citation of the source.

b) Manuela is planning a new wave of the GLES pre-election cross-section for the 2026 Bundestag election. She wants to import the GLES area code cross-section metadata from the 2021 survey into her Colectica question floor editor. It generates a sample of all URI from the

³⁴ <https://search.gesis.org>

2021 survey from the study documentation and imports all question metadata into the questionnaire editor.

- **Automatic access to variable data using scripts**

In the sense of FAIR, a valuable machine-actionable feature allowed by a PID is direct access. The automatic access to the data in a dataset is enabled by a code or a script (i.e., using R, Stata, SPSS). When executed can retrieve the exact data represented through the PID. It is possible to access a variable or a group of variables via PID with a few steps:

1. Establish a direct connection to R or similar using codes informing PIDs;
2. The code return could be a CSV file, SPSS file, or STATA file with the specific data identified in the PID(s);
3. Integration with GESIS Notebooks is possible.

The direct access feature would be highly relevant for harmonisation tools within its code packages. These tools do not provide data but a set of scripts and do-files that calculate response scales and provide harmonised measures and equivalent rates for similar variables among different studies. When using those tools, the researchers are responsible for getting access to the datasets directly from the data providers. With unique identifiers assigned to each variable and these codes embedded with the variable's PIDs, the data could be automatically accessed, making it easier to use dozens of harmonised variables of the same topic from numerous diverse instruments. Some harmonisation tools' projects led by GESIS are described.

3.2.2. QuestionLink tool

QuestionLink is a tool that provides recording scripts with which data on selected concepts can be harmonised across different measurement instruments. This addresses the problem of different surveys often using different question wording or response scales to capture the same concepts. QuestionLink thus helps researchers find data on selected constructs and then allows them to pool German data on the concept across time and many large survey programs. However, both accessing the relevant data as well as applying the correct recording script require that researchers can find the appropriate variables in the many source data sets. Here, PIDs on a variable level would enrich QuestionLink and make the service easier to use. In this use case, the PID registration service is used to assign PIDs for the Political interest pre-harmonized variables that come from seven measurement instruments: German General Social Survey - (ALLBUScompact)³⁵, Cross-Section 2009-2017 - (GLES)³⁶, GESIS Panel - Standard Edition (GPANEL)³⁷, International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government II -

³⁵ GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften (2021). German General Social Survey (ALLBUScompact) - Cumulation 1980-2018. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA5277 Data file Version 1.1.0, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13775>.

³⁶ GLES (2020). GLES Cross-Section 2009-2017, Cumulation. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA6835 Data file Version 1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13648>.

³⁷ GESIS (2022). GESIS Panel - Standard Edition. GESIS, Cologne. ZA5665 Data file Version 43.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13880>.

(ISSP, 1990)³⁸, European Social Survey – (ESS)³⁹, National Educational Panel Study (NEPS)⁴⁰ and The Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)⁴¹.

Figure 9–QuestionLink Instruments for pre-harmonized Political interest variables

These instruments selected 68 political interest variables before they were used for harmonisation purposes. Some surveys only have one variable name for several years, whereas others have different variable names per wave. Since the exact question formulation and response labels differ slightly through data collection and because they register the same concepts, there is a high risk of ambiguous citation when trying to differentiate variables used in the same survey over the years.

Table 3, for example, refers to the variable’s name similarity within ALLBUS instruments in different years range. The PID (DOI) identifies only the Dataset, not the variable, and their names are significantly similar.

Survey	Instrument	Wave	Year range	Variable Name	DOI
ALLBUS	ALLBUS B 10pt	cumulation	1982—1988	pa02	10.4232/1.13775
ALLBUS	ALLBUS A 5pt	cumulation	1980—2018	pa02a	10.4232/1.13775

Table 3 – QuestionLink Example 1: Variables names similarity in ALLBUS survey.

The PID assigned for pre-harmonization variables in the QuestionLink tool uniquely identifies individual variables per survey, wave, and year. It also prevents ambiguity due to the repetitive variable’s name, which can be confusing and lead the reader into error. Some surveys only have one variable name across several years. Differentiating these variables using unique PIDs is essential because they do not carry the same values and responses. Their data collected throughout the years can differ according to the values, scales, and quantity.

³⁸ ISSP Research Group (1992). International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government II – ISSP 1990. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA1950 Data file Version 1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.1950>

³⁹ <https://ess-search.nsd.no/CDW/ConceptVariables>

⁴⁰ National Educational Panel Study (NEPS): Starting Cohort 6 – Adults, doi:10.5157/NEPS:SC6:6.0.1

⁴¹ Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), data for years 1984–2019, SOEP-Core v36, EU Edition, 2021, doi:10.5684/soep.core.v36eu

Table 4 shows some examples and the slight differences among variable naming. As a matter of example only, the PID Proposals listed in table 4 are all fictitious and provided as mere examples. They do not represent any PID syntax assigned to any data holder, dataset, or variable.

Dataset
DOI

Variable
PID

Survey	Instrument	Wave	Year range	Variable Name	DOI	Variable PID
ALLBUS	ALLBUS A 5pt	cumulation	1980–2018	pa02a	10.4232/1.13775	21.T11991/ALLBUS-pa02a
ALLBUS	ALLBUS B 10pt	cumulation	1982–1988	pa02	10.4232/1.13775	22.T11992/ALLBUS-pa02
ESS	ESS 4pt	cumulation	2002–2018	polintr	10.21338/NSD-ESS-CUMULATIVE	23.T11997/ESS-polintr
EVS	EVS 4pt	cumulation	1990–2017	E023	10.4232/1.13736	24.T11998/EVS-E023
GPANEL	GPANEL 8pt	ca	2015	caav068a	10.4232/1.13785	24.T11998/GPANEL-caav068a
GPANEL	GPANEL 8pt	cd	2015	cdav035a	10.4232/1.13785	24.T11998/GPANEL-cdav035a
GPANEL	GPANEL 8pt	da	2016	daav088a	10.4232/1.13785	24.T11998/GPANEL-daav088a
ISSP	ALLBUS A 5pt	Role of Government III	1996	v46	10.4232/1.2900	25.T11991/ISSP-v46
ISSP	ALLBUS A 5pt	Role of Government V	2016	v46	10.4232/1.13052	25.T11991/ISSP-v46
NEPS	ESS 4pt	6	2013	t516105	10.5157/NEPS:SC6:6.0.1	10.5157/NEPS-6-t516105
NEPS	ESS 4pt	10	2017	t516105	10.5157/NEPS:SC6:6.0.2	10.5157/NEPS-10-t516105
NEPS	ESS 4pt	11	2018	t516105	10.5157/NEPS:SC6:6.0.3	10.5157/NEPS-11-t516105
NEPS	ESS 4pt	12	2019	t516105	10.5157/NEPS:SC6:6.0.4	10.5157/NEPS-12-t516105
SOEP	SOEP 4pt	bp	1985	bp75	10.5684/soep.core.v36eu	10.5684/soep-bp-bp75
SOEP	SOEP 4pt	cp	1986	cp75	10.5684/soep.core.v36eu	10.5684/soep-cp-cp75

Table 4 – QuestionLink Example 3: Variables list with Proposed PIDs examples.

Other projects within GESIS are selected as use cases. The ONBound and GESIS HaSpaD projects are two use cases for assigning PID for variables for harmonisation purposes.

3.2.3. The GESIS ONBound project

The ONBound project, “Old and new boundaries: National Identities and Religion⁴²”, is the Harmonisation Wizard compiling a custom dataset and supporting analysis on the two projects’ core elements: National and religious identity. The ONBound data aim to promote an understanding of national and religious identities’ interdependencies in many countries, and researchers can compare different instruments measurements for the same topics and subjects. The database contains 1650 variables for the country-level data from 17⁴³ datasets from 1945 to 2019. At the individual level, the ONBound project has so far harmonised 750 variables out of

⁴²<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/onbound>

⁴³ [Religion and Nation in Constitutions Worldwide](#), [Religion and State Project, Round 3](#), [Migration Integration Policy Index 2015](#), [Indicators of Citizenship Rights for Immigrants](#), [The IMPIC Project: Immigration Policies in Comparison \(Indicator Scores\)](#), [World Development Indicators](#), [UNHCR Statistics](#), [Polity IV Project, Political Regime Characteristics and Transitions, 1800–2018 \(Polity IV Annual Time-Series, 1800–2018\)](#), [Democratic Electoral Systems around the world, 1946–2016](#), [CIRI Human Rights Data Project](#), [KOF Globalization Index](#), [Religious Characteristics of States Dataset Project, Demographics, version 2.0 \(RCS–Dem 2.0\): Countries Only](#), [Church Attendance and Religious Change Pooled European Dataset \[unpublished dataset\]](#), [United Nations: Demographic Statistics Database \(Religious Affiliations\)](#), [World Religion Project – National Religion Dataset](#), [Religious Diversity Index](#), [The Ethnic Power Relations \(EPR\) Core Dataset 2019](#).

1500 source variables from 18 studies from 1970 until 2018⁴⁴. The National identity consists of a set of variables on the following constructs:

National identity: Formal Membership / Citizenship; Origin Respondent and Family; Feeling of Belonging / Self Identification; Membership; Boundaries; National Pride.

Religious identity encompasses a more extensive set of variables: Religious identity: Formal Membership; Denominations; Practices; Belief; Religiosity; Centrality of Religion in Life; Attitudes Towards Religion; Religion and Nation; Tolerance Towards Different Groups of Community; Discrimination; Racism; and Civic Attitudes (Support for Regime Principles, Regime Performance, Regime Institutions, Politics, Immigration, Subnational Region).

The country-level related data offer variables on the following topics: Policies (Constitutions: Religions, National Identity, Context) Policy Settings (Religion, Integration, Immigration); State Indicators (Economy, Standard of Living, Politics & Polity, Special Topics: Human Rights, Globalisation); Civil Society (Population: Basic Population Figures, Migration, Education) Religion (Religious Relevance); Diversity (Religious Diversity, Ethnic Diversity).

The ONBound Harmonisation Wizard provides a set of cumulation and harmonisation by topics and scope of research data. The project documentation⁴⁵ has a list of variable IDs that correspond to the ONBound Variable name (Varname), variable label (Varlabel), the codings and notes on harmonisation steps. The harmonisation process required the possible data sources identification and common variables from these sources.

A coding scheme was created since some variables were too dissimilar, so different versions of that variable were coded (e.g. *natid_pride1a*, *natid_pride1b*, *natid_pride1c*). For many variables, it was also generated as a general harmonised variable (e.g. *natid_pride1*). Table 5 provides some examples of the possible ambiguity in variable naming within the ONBound Project.

Variable ID Master_Matrix	ONBound Variable name	ONBound Variable Label	Target Coding
1400 National pride			
1410 General National Pride			
1201	natid_pride1	National Identity: Pride1: How proud being [NATIONALITY], harmonised 4-p. pride	(1) Very proud ... (4) Not proud at all
1201	natid_pride1a	National Identity: Pride1: How proud are you being [NATIONALITY], 4-p. pride	(1) Very proud ... (4) Not proud at all
1201	natid_pride1b	National Identity: Pride1: How proud are you being [NATIONALITY], 7-p. pride	(1) Not at all ... (7) A Lot
1201	natid_pride1c	National Identity: Pride1: How proud are you being [NATIONALITY], 5-p. agree	(1) Strongly disagree ... (5) Strongly agree

⁴⁴ May, Antonia, Werhan, Katharina, Bechert, Insa and Quandt, Markus (2020): ONBound User Guide. Retrieved from <https://onbound.gesis.org/wizard> [22.07.2022].

⁴⁵ONBound (2019/07/01): 'ONBound Macro-Level-Data_Documentation'. Retrieved from <https://www.onbound.international/DATAOverview.aspx> [22.07.2022].

1202	natic_pride2	National Identity: Pride2: Proud being citizen of [COUNTRY]	(1) Very proud ... (-6) Do not understand the question
1206	natic_pride3	National Identity: Pride3: I like how we are [NATIONALITY]	(1) Strongly agree ... (4) Strongly disagree

Table 5: Possible ambiguity on variable naming within the ONBound Project.

The OnBound coding scheme encompasses a complex harmonisation process to provide similar information enabling the comparison of such diverse elements: two levels of data, individual and national, which data we collected using different instruments, research methods, and approaches. Even though the same surveys were repeated across the years, the same variable was not always present. If so, identifying elements such as names or labels can be diverse without mentioning the thoroughly distinct scales and levels of measurements among surveys and instruments.

The detail, accuracy, and adherence ensured in developing the coding scheme englobe standardised designation for countries and sub-regions, religious denominations, and political parties. At the individual level, naming and labelling variables followed a set of rules to ensure data level identification, topic and subtopic covered, version control, and scale harmonisation. For example, the variable name *pol_interest1b* refers to the main topic of *politics* (*pol*) and the concept of political interest (interest), with the first political interest measurement (1) with the scaling version b. The label also contains information on the character of the variable: “Politics: Political interest1: How interested in politics, 5-p. interest”. In this example, the topic (“Politics”), including the measured concept („Political interest”), the measurement version (“1: How interested in politics”), and scaling information of this version which measures from 1 to 5 (“5-p. interest”).

The country-level variable naming and labelling rules also embedded information on the main topic and subtopic, including the original variable name and the acronym for the dataset source. In the given example, the OnBoung country-level variable name is POL_MIG_AVGS_E01_IMPIC, where POL means (Policies), the main topic, and the sub-topic MIG (Migration), AVGS_E01 is the original variable name, and IMPIC (The Immigration Policies in Comparison) is the dataset. Country-level variables can also include the elicitation mode, the continuity, and timely data coverage in their names.

Besides the naming and labelling, data format, scales, country codes, and other relevant concepts such as religion and political parties are not only a very complex and time-consuming process to do but also to understand. The comprehension of data and its interlinks is crucial to proper reuse. One of the barriers to reusing data is the researchers' afraid of misunderstanding or misinterpreting data and then being led to errors or incorrect inferences⁴⁶.

The ONBound User Guide provides instructions on understanding the data harmonisation procedures and repository and how to use the ONBound Harmonisation Wizard, guiding the user through the phases and techniques needed to compile an ONBound dataset until the

⁴⁶ KIM, Youngseek. *Scientific Data Reuse Survey [Dataset]*. Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor]. 2017. <http://doi.org/10.3886/E100404V1>.

citation step⁴⁷. However, the citation relies on the customised data and the original data sources citation. For copyright reasons, these data sources downloaded are mandatory to create and use the harmonised ONBound data set. The documentation also provides these sources with citation examples⁴⁸. Nevertheless, citing the ONBound compiled dataset and related data sources is not enough to identify the variables reused precisely. Besides, collecting a complete ONBound dataset including all linked sources at once is not recommended⁴⁹, this approach is not feasible. In this sense, due to a complex set of rules and standards to identify the variables, assigning a PID to each one of them makes citation and data retrieval significantly more precise, easier, and faster. This solution favours the data users and the ONBound project due to the actionable-machine features that such identification allows.

3.2.4. GESIS HaSpaD

Similar to UNBound, Harmonising and synthesising partnership histories from different research data infrastructures projects (HaSpaD⁵⁰) does not provide data sets for downloads. Instead, it provides a syntax package that harmonises source datasets from survey programs provided by data repositories. The HaSpaD does provide the selection, cumulation, and harmonisation of partnership biographies from surveys in Germany, including the following topics: Partnership biographies (of all selected survey programs are always included): respondent's biography data with sociodemographic characteristics, family background, religion. Additional variables at the respondent and partner level, such as dates of birth, citizenship, education, and religious denomination, but also information on divorce and separation of the respondent's parents, are part of the harmonised variables offered in addition to the couple biographies. The survey programs include Panel Analysis of Intimate Relationships and Family Dynamics (pairfam)⁵¹, Cumulated German General Social Survey (ALLBUS) 1980–2016⁵², Family Survey (FS)⁵³, Mannheim Divorce Study 1996 (MSS)⁵⁴, Fertility and Family Survey (FFS)⁵⁵, German Life History Study (GLHS)⁵⁶, Generations and Gender Survey (GGS)⁵⁷, Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)⁵⁸ and Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)⁵⁹.

Once the interested variables and dataset are selected, the HaSpaD - Harmonisation Wizard harmonises data sources to create a comprehensive final dataset, including extra variables for all survey programs. The interested party needs to download the original datasets from each selected survey and follow the instructions provided to run do-files codes to manage the dataset and create a specific sub-dataset with target surveys and variables.

⁴⁷ May, Antonia, Werhan, Katharina, Bechert, Insa and Quandt, Markus (2020): ONBound User Guide. Retrieved from <https://onbound.gesis.org/wizard> [22.07.2022].

⁴⁸ ONBound (2020): 'ONBound_Documentation_Macro_v4.0'. Retrieved <https://onbound.gesis.org/wizard> [22.07.2022].

⁴⁹ May, Antonia, Werhan, Katharina, Bechert, Insa and Quandt, Markus (2020): ONBound User Guide. Retrieved from <https://onbound.gesis.org/wizard> [22.07.2022].

⁵⁰<https://www.gesis.org/en/services/processing-and-analyzing-data/data-harmonization/harmonizing-and-synthesizing-partnership-histories>

⁵¹ <https://www.pairfam.de/en/>

⁵² <https://www.gesis.org/en/allbus/allbus-home>

⁵³ <https://www.dji.de/ueber-uns/projekte/projekte/familienurvey.html>

⁵⁴ <https://www.mzes.uni-mannheim.de/d7/en/projects/determinants-of-divorce>

⁵⁵ <https://www.bib.bund.de/EN/Research/Surveys/FFS/family-and-fertility-survey.html>

⁵⁶ <https://www.mpib-berlin.mpg.de/research/concluded-areas/center-for-sociology-and-the-study-of-the-life-course>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ggp-i.org/>

⁵⁸ <http://www.share-project.org/home0.html>

⁵⁹ https://www.diw.de/en/diw_01.c.678568.en/research_data_center_soep.html

The HaSpad Manual⁶⁰ instructs researchers on how to cite the HaSpad-data and all used original data sources and the documentation of variables' sources. It provides helpful citation guidelines for the harmonised survey programs. However, the data citations are designed to identify the complete survey's datasets. The HaSpad-data wizard aims to harmonise a chosen set of variables on biographical data from survey-based longitudinal data on partnership biographies. Depending on the selected variables, they might not be available within all surveys. For instance, table 6 shows while the variables Anchor's sex, month and year of birth, and citizenship(s) are available for all studies within the survey program (green check), on the other hand, variables such as Partner's month and year of birth, citizenship(s) and level of education variables are not available for all partial studies (orange check) or are not available for any partial study (red check). In this sense, not all variables selected within a survey will be available and, therefore, used. Thus, citing the complete dataset does not reflect the exact data reused.

Selected variables	pairfam	ALLBUS	Family Surveys	Mannheim Divorce Study	Fertility and Family Survey	German Life History Study	Generations and Gender Survey	SHARE	SOEP
Sociodemographic characteristics									
Anchor's sex	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Anchor's month and year of birth	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Anchor's citizenship(s)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Partner's month and year of birth	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✗
Partner's citizenship(s)	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
Partner's highest level of education	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	●	✗	✓	✗

Table 6 - Variables availability within selected data sets - HaSpad harmonisation wizard.

Many waves are available from the nine studies, and datasets' variables can vastly vary. The couple biography variables across surveys are:

- Beginning cohabitation (cohbeg).
- Beginning marriage (marbeg).
- Beginning relationship (relbeg).
- Date of partner's death (dop).
- End cohabitation (cohend).
- End marriage (marend).
- End relationship (relend).

Within each study, these variables are sometimes limited to one or two years/seasons or even missing values due to the study's design. Not only do the names change across studies but also measures and scales, values and date formats, and so on. Once the HaSpaD has provided the

⁶⁰ Schulz, S., Weiß, B., Sterl, S., Haensch, A.-C., Schmid, L., & May, A. (2021). HaSpaD - Data Manual (September 2021). (GESIS Papers, 2021/12). Köln: GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften. <https://doi.org/10.21241/ssoar.75135>

harmonised files for the selected variables, the original or the source variable must carry its unique identifier to be immediately retrieved. Since the wizard tool uses two core elements to provide the harmonised dataset, both need to have a PID assigned. The first element is the original variables from as many studies as the researcher has chosen. The second element is the *do-files*, the code used to manage the source dataset, which carries the commands to deliver a new dataset formatted on specific rules over the original variables.

3.3. German Institute for Economic Research (DIW)

The German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) is based at the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW⁶¹). The SOEP-Core⁶² is the main piece of the Socio-Economic Panel and yearly surveys the living situation and attitudes of more than 15,000 households and about 30,000 people since 1984. The study „*Leben in Deutschland*“ (“Living in Germany”) is the largest longitudinal (long-term) study of social developments in Germany, being enlarged in 1990 due to the German reunification to encompass a sample from East Germany. The 560 available datasets provide information on all household members: Germans living in the former eastern and western German states, foreign citizens, and immigrants residing in Germany. Since 2016 the study has been widened with a sample of refugees. Some topics include household composition, occupational biographies, employment, earnings, health and satisfaction indicators, distributed 21.280 questions, 309 instruments and 101.574 variables⁶³.

“Living in Germany” is an umbrella term that covers many sub-samples and questionnaires regarding households and people. The household-related questions investigate the financial issues and utilities within the house and all general dwelling conditions. Personal questionnaires cover working life, leisure activities, political interests, people moving in, newborn family members, child's education and their parents' participation, preteens, teens, and young specific questions related to their personalities, social networks, interests and education. For instance, in the survey year 2019, a total of 59 field instruments, one contact protocol, and 58 questionnaires were used. In this sense, this is a complex study in terms of variable structure, and many relations can be linked between variables through questionnaires, sample instruments, waves, and years. The variable list in CSV format is available here⁶⁴.

The DIW office in Berlin registers the SOEP-Core complexity information through extensive documentation on Topics of SOEP-Core, survey design, data editions and distribution files, and orientation on how to use the SOEP-Core data through the SOEPcompanion⁶⁵ website. The data and variable details are provided by the Paneldata⁶⁶ interface, where variable landing pages are available. For instance, figure 10 depicts the variable *bip_171*⁶⁷, which measures *Interest in Politics*, and has a landing page with variable values and the relations in a timeline overview.

⁶¹ www.diw.de

⁶² [10.5684/soep.core.v37i](https://doi.org/10.5684/soep.core.v37i).

⁶³ <https://paneldata.org/soep-core/>

⁶⁴ <https://github.com/paneldata/soep-core/blob/master/metadata/variables.csv>

⁶⁵ <http://companion.soep.de/index.html>

⁶⁶ <https://paneldata.org/soep-core/>

⁶⁷ https://paneldata.org/soep-core/datasets/bip/bip_171

bip/bip_171: Interest in Politics

Figure 10: Variable graph: *bip/bip_171*: Interest in Politics⁶⁸

The variable landing page also registers the associations with other variables with the same concept, shown in table 7. The documented connections describe the variable name, the file name of the dataset, and the label definitions across related variables to identify changes over time in surveys.

Year	Related Variable	Year	Related Variable	Year	Related Variable	Year	Related Variable
0	pl/plh0007	1992	ip/ip89	2002	sp/sp110	2012	bcp/bcp124
1984	--	1993	jp/jp89	2003	tp/tp117	2013	bdp/bdp130
1985	bp/bp75	1994	kp/kp91	2004	up/up122	2014	bep/bep118
1986	cp/cp75	1995	lp/lp97	2005	vp/vp128	2015	bfp/bfp143
1987	dp/dp84	1996	mp/mp83	2006	wp/wp118	2016	bgp/bgp143
1988	ep/ep73	1997	np/np93	2007	xp/xp127	2017	bhp/bhp_182
1989	fp/fp89	1998	op/op96	2008	yp/yp129	2018	bip/bip_171
1990	gp/gp83	1999	pp/pp110	2009	zp/zp122	2019	bjp/bjp_167
1990	gpost/gp50e	2000	qp/qp115	2010	bap/bap127	2020	bkp/bkp_169
1991	hp/hp89	2001	rp/rp110	2011	bbp/bbp128	--	--

Table 7: Variable relationships in SOEP timeline⁶⁹

The SOEP-Core has a highly complex data structure, containing a multitude of different datasets, and variables are used across such a long-term investigation, and assigning a PID to identify them would it be relevant as use cases:

⁶⁸ https://paneldata.org/soep-core/datasets/bip/bip_171

⁶⁹ https://paneldata.org/soep-core/datasets/bip/bip_171

- a. Track and get advantages of machine-actionable features, monitoring the scientific output of a given variable.
- b. Since the study is vast and addresses several themes, PIDs enable tracking of the variable's specific uses by subject by target types, such as household or people-related information in academic publications. This particular follow-up would carry out a more detailed evaluation of the dataset's usage, leading to improved decisions on services and the usefulness of the data.
- c. Search and connect information from other datasets that use the same variable with a different label. This approach is particularly relevant for a variable used for the harmonisation process with others within the same study and other studies, such as the Political interest set of variables used in the QuestionLink tool.
- d. An expressive amount of variables is already documented at <https://paneldata.org/>. Each SOEP-core variable is uniquely documented and has a web page. Registering this page as the landing page of the variables PID would speed up the registration PID process, linking automatically to related datasets and fostering findability.

3.4. Qualiservice (University of Bremen)

Qualiservice is a data service centre for qualitative empirical social research, which makes research data available for secondary use. The research data consist primarily of qualitative interview transcripts and context data, which documents the primary data collected during the research process. Qualiservice structures and homogenised data through metadata, registering a metadata set to enable content understanding. The Qualiservice system generates metadata elements according to the DDI 3.2 standard and defines mandatory core elements and optional elements to add a more precise description. Qualiservice's metadata schema is already compatible with the data registration agency for the social and economic agency (dalra), which registration service is being enlarged to register PIDs at a lower granularity level.

The primary purpose of this use case is to provide PIDs for an accurate citation of data objects being registered, such as interview transcripts. Previously recommending the citation of entire studies, the level with the PID (DOI), represented as a hyperlink in the quotation. Beyond identifying the Study as a whole, when citing contextual materials or Individual interviews, the Object type ("name of the material" or "Interview") should be provided, along with the Study DOI. "The DOI of the study is also to be cited for individual interviews in order to get to it more quickly" (Qualiservice MetadatenSchema 1.1, 2014, p.9⁷⁰).

The current cooperation PANGAEA-Qualiservice requires that the previous citation concept has been updated, and the DOIs are now subject to identifying dataset entities instead of the study level. The data collection or dataset can be a collection of data (interviews, observations) but also in a particular file version (video, texts, audio files, or a mixture of these) or organised by a given survey method.

⁷⁰ Betancort Cabrera, Noemi and Haake, Elmar (2013): The Qualiservice Metadata Schema, Version 1.1. Qualiservice Technical Reports, 2014/02. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:gbv:46-00103643-13>.

Another data arrangement, the "Parent dataset, " groups a set of datasets. The data collection can hold all the study data together, or some part of the study data and a given wave data can exist in several data collections.

Listed below are some examples of data complexity at Qualiservice:

- a. Study dataset - encompass all data of the three phases of the study that have been published under one data collection: <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.930449>;
- b. Dataset with the partial data collected on one of the four different survey sites: The data from the GloPro study collected in Beijing - <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939235>; There are three other datasets, such as the one from the Netherlands: <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939238>;
- c. Dataset of data collected using a specific survey method: in the Mangroves and Meaning-Making study (<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.930138>), other data were also collected, such as Transect Walks (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.930180>);
- d. A "Parent" dataset, which does not group data objects but collects other datasets. These parent sets can be used when the individual data collections are only reusable in conjunction with the others. One of the associated datasets (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.938536>) collects the chat logs (<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.938581>), but these can only be understood in conjunction with the interviews (<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.938537>) and the field notes (<https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.938576>);
- e. Data set containing the data of a single wave/phase of a study: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.921823>.

Due to this complex set of files, formats and data configurations, Qualiservice had to develop a detailed citation guideline, considering the high level of potential ambiguity. This approach relies on a detailed-oriented user citation practice, which increases the risk of a mistaken or incomplete citation. At a lower level below the dataset, the contextual materials or Individual interviews are elements of a data collection or dataset required for citation. Each dataset gets a DOI, and individual interviews citation, for example, would follow an extended ID. The extended (Qualiservice) ID follows, in most cases, the same syntax pattern, formed by the Study Acronym, the Wave Number (or Acronym), and the Interview Number (StudyAcronym_WaveNumber_InterviewNumber). For instance: a URI (a concrete URL) for the data object could be: https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.946345#MainLife_03-LG_1-590⁷¹, where MainLife is the StudyAcronym, the 03 is the wave/phase number and LG_1-590 the data object number.

However, only the columns "Data ID" or "Case ID", are not enough to disambiguate a given data file. Even Though it is best always to use Data/Case ID, it may be important to cite the exact file because different versions or parts of the same interview are recorded in the dataset using the same ID but naming files differently. For this reason, the "File name" (also File ID) is added in the citation. Bellow, there is and citation example using the File Name ID because there are multiple files for the same Data/Case ID:

Sommer, Ilka; Weingartz, Sarah; Elçin, Melih; Tuncel, Bilge; Weiß, Anja (2021): Globalising medical knowledge and practice: Doctor-patient-interaction videos observed at a university hospital in Ankara (Turkey). Transcripts, translation, audiovisual and context

⁷¹ Habermas, Tilmann (2022): MainLife: Entwicklung der Lebensgeschichte. Transkripte der Erzählungen. FDZ Qualiservice, Bremen. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.946345>.

material. FDZ Qualiservice, Bremen. Simulation interview (2019). GLOPRO_ANK_06, data file GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Hakan_02 (video). https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.939234#GLOPRO_ANK_06.

Table 8 breaks down the metadata and shows the example of two files with the same ID with different file names.

Data ID	File name	File format	Data format	Language	DC date	Location
GLOPRO_ANK_06	GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Hakan_01	mts	Video	tur	2019	Ankara
GLOPRO_ANK_06	GLOPRO_RAW_ANK_Hakan_02	mts	Video	tur	2019	Ankara

Table 8 - files naming at Qualiservice examples

Considering the complex data structure, evolving a wide range of data files and formats, assigning a PID to identify each data entity will simplify the FAIR management of Qualiservice data. The relevant use cases here are:

- a. The data structure in Qualiservice differs from tabular data, given its attributes, such as text, videos, and description data.
- b. PIDs can be assigned to identify the data level the provider considers most relevant. Data files grouped in sets, such as datasets or collections, can still keep their PIDs assigned to identify the related data of a given study as a whole;
- c. However, considering their data types and file naming, a PID at the data file level would solve this problem for disambiguating similar data files. This unique identifier will give the user a straightforward way of citing, identifying, and getting the target file.
- d. Since PIDs are machine-actionable elements, Qualiservice and its users can take advantage of automatic features when assigning PIDs at datafile levels, such as linking related data files within the same or from different studies and getting direct access to them.

Each use case has its specificities that we addressed in the previous examples. Nonetheless, there are common advantages and benefits for the RDCs and their users, consolidated in the conclusion section.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we addressed the lower granularity level of a dataset through two different attributes: (1) tabular data as a variable element; (2) qualitative data as an individual data file within a dataset. We addressed use case partners' needs on registering PIDs below the dataset and study levels. The PID for variables registration service is suitable for solutions based on

each use case partner's need. Considering the particularities of data attributes, we have set the metadata schema accordingly.

Use cases on the PID assignments are large and small datasets, individual or sets of variables examples. For instance, the Gesis Data Archive platform holds more than 500,000 variables from national and international studies, covering the Social Sciences, Economics, and Behaviour Sciences domains. In the Education domain, we addressed the PIDs for single variables, the complex relationship with differentiation variables, and the intersected analyses from the digital reporting system at DZHW.

We provided three examples of harmonization tools, which service does not provide data but only harmonizes them for comparability purposes, i.e., the QuestionLink Harmonisation tool, the ONBound Harmonisation Wizard and the HaSpaD - Harmonizing and synthesizing partnership histories. In this sense, the service provides PIDs for the scripts or do-files that harmonise variables and the original sources behind the proposed harmonisation. Similar to the Gesis Search, we explained the PID assignment for each variable at the SOEP-Core v37. This dataset contains more than 100.000 variables from more than 300 instruments regarding the study "Living in Germany" for the last 30 years.

As a second approach, to assign PIDs for attributes other than variables, i.e., qualitative data files, we present one use case. Even though this approach was not addressed in the original KonsortSWD proposal, we have found it helpful to describe since it is one use case partner need. The use case for qualitative data is the Qualiservice, part of QualidataNet within KonsortSWD; we proposed assigning a PID for qualitative data organized in files regarding transcripts, translation, audiovisual, and context material for doctor-patient-interaction videos observed. In this sense, RDCs can take advantage of machine-actionable features inherent to PIDs, for instance, promoting practical solutions:

- disambiguating variables and qualitative object types for citation purposes;
- tracking data usage through unambiguous citation;
- relating similar variables with different labels and names across waves;
- directly connects variables used in the harmonization process within different studies;
- mapping automatically relations between variables, datasets and other documented entities;
- applying interactive resources such as do-files and scripts to get direct access to the data, under certain requirements.

Those are some functionalities which require persistent identifiers to be implemented. This range of solutions would maximize the end-user perceived value of RDCs since their data would better impact the research landscape. This user-centred approach would also benefit the RDCs by fostering their data findability, accessibility and usage. The resulting improved performance of RDCs would increase their credibility, scientific relevance and funding opportunities. In addition, our approach drives open science by turning the FAIR principles into enhanced research data practices.

5. Potential future Work

There is an increasing potential for future use and applications for variables and other attributes assigned with PIDs. Beyond the use cases that actually concern data citation and granularity level itself, some facts using PIDs arise with a fundamental impact on the research community. Even not foreseen in the KonsortSWD deliverables, data citations can also be employed to calculate research impact, comparable to bibliographic citations. When precisely measured, how variables' citation affects the dataset's impact can be tracked. Citation indexes (still) represent the evidence of the scientific output's relevance and are the reward evaluation criteria in the academy. Tracking and measuring usage rates of the datasets, mainly through entities PIDs (variables from statistics datasets or qualitative data files), will grow researchers' authorship of their work, increasing their recognition. Since the variable PID contains the original study DOI, connecting related entities from different but complementary results is possible, converging into researchers' authority and impact.

Data users may also find it valuable to correspond dataset elements, such as variables, to explore the consistency or comparability of a variable over time across waves and studies. With machine-readable and actionable features, complex recommendation systems can be built to show relationships between variables with other entries into relationship maps, such as knowledge graph representations. Research outputs are increasingly interdependent, interconnecting many entities from different levels (e.g. study units, instruments, questions, response scales, and variables) into knowledge graphs. In this sense, documenting and describing all these relations will enrich the data reuse by supporting search and browse functionality.

The PID Registration Service does not aim to provide knowledge graph visualization itself. However, since the PID registration service has included in its metadata schema⁷² the *Related_Item* field and its corresponding subfields (*Related_Item_Identifier*; *Related_Item_Identifier_Type*; *Relation_Type*), Thus, documenting the variables with those information enables a further application to enhance knowledge graph visualization in the future (see Section 5 on potential future work) because the relations are already set through this *relations_type* field and subfields.

Any other interested person or scientist from the research community will easily find the usable variable according to their research needs. Within data holders, this approach can endeavour to maximize value-added services from increasingly interdependent and interconnecting entities of research outputs. Both statistical variables and qualitative file formats are associated with more than one entity. Some examples are studies, published papers, data papers, or reports on Data Management Plans. Variables are linked to their inherent elements (e.g., questions, questionnaires or instruments, waves survey and response scales) and can also be input for interactive resources (Scripts, Do-files, etc.). It could also point to registering and assigning PIDs to questions and response schemas (e.g., response scales such as the Likert scale) from existing surveys for reuse purposes. Documenting and describing all these relations in the appropriate cataloguing relations type fields will enrich the data reuse by supporting search and browse functionalities, fostering the FAIR principles through a metadata-driven research ecosystem.

⁷² Bach, Janete Saldanha, Klas, Claus-Peter & Mutschke, Peter. (2023, January 31). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: metadata schema extended report. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588902>.

5.1. KonsortSWD TA5 M1 further steps

The PID registration service for finer granular elements below the study level is a highly flexible tool. The open-source code and documentation allow reuse and can be quickly adjusted for different entity registration. The envisioned metadata schema complies with international standards. It can therefore be adjustable in the future to accommodate other elements such as survey questions, response schema, or any other entity that can benefit data reuse and interoperability. The next steps are the implementation of the described use cases for PIDs on the attribute level the and integration of a flexible component to handle different metadata schemas.

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